

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 8.7

Liaison with related projects and initiatives: Intermediate report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the activities of alignment of HEREDITARY with other initiatives with similar or complementary objectives carried out by EBC between month 1 and month 20 in the framework of the Task 8.4 (Liaison with related projects and initiatives) under Work Package 8 (Exploitation, Innovation, Communication and Dissemination). Through the engagement of stakeholders relevant to the project scope, HEREDITARY liaison activities aim to promote coordination and collaboration among related EU and global initiatives by:

- Generating synergies between EU research networks
- Identifying and addressing mutual drivers and barriers
- Accelerating the exchange of experience and knowledge

As lead of HEREDITARY liaison activities, EBC has facilitated relations with relevant EU players to foster the mainstreaming of innovative EU brain research in policymaking.

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1 Introduction

Over the past decade, increasing EU funding for brain research has enabled the emergence of numerous projects with innovative potential. Despite major advances in brain research, valuable findings may still fail to reach or impact real-world practice, limiting their potential benefit. Liaison activities bring together EU and global projects and initiatives with similar or complementary objectives to enhance synergies and avoid overlap of activities.

Running from January 2024 to December 2027, HEREDITARY (HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY) is an EU-funded research project aiming to harmonise clinical, genomic and environmental data to provide deeper insight into the gut-brain axis and its impact on neurodegenerative disorders.

As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, HEREDITARY seeks to empower the development of more effective treatment and diagnosis strategies through advanced federated analytics.

Figure 1 HEREDITARY methodology - five-layered structure

As part of HEREDITARY Work Package 8 (Exploitation, Innovation, Communication and Dissemination), Task 8.4 (Liaison with related projects and initiatives) focuses on strengthening cooperation between HEREDITARY and relevant EU projects and initiatives. To this end, the European Brain Council (EBC) has been leveraging, as Task Leader, its extensive network of key players in the EU brain space (encompassing patient organisations, scientific and professional societies as well as industry partners).

2 Methodology

HEREDITARY liaison with related projects and initiatives follows a stepwise approach:

1. Mapping of projects addressing multimodal health data integration, neurodegenerative disorders and the gut-brain axis
2. Shortlist of projects and initiatives relevant to HEREDITARY scope
3. Identification of common interest points and potential areas of collaboration
4. Design and implementation of a liaison plan

2.1 Mapping of projects addressing multimodal health data integration, neurodegenerative disorders and the gut-brain axis

Modern societies generate a significant amount of data (real-world data). Linking health-related real-world data and research data from multiple sources (multimodal health data integration) has showed high potential in numerous disease areas including neurodegenerative disorders. HEREDITARY and other projects similar in nature and goals participate, altogether, in harnessing the value of health data to, ultimately, advance medical research and improve patient outcomes.

In the early stages of the project, EBC put together and provided the consortium with a comprehensive list of 15 potentially relevant projects with a focus on multimodal health data integration, neurodegenerative disorders and the gut-brain axis:

- Projects funded under the same topic as HEREDITARY: HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-04 - Better integration and use of health-related real-world and research data, including genomics, for improved clinical outcomes
 - [WISDOM](#) – Well-being improvement through the Integration of healthcare and reSearch Data and models with Out border for chronic iMmune-mediated diseases
 - [BETTER](#) – Federated learning framework for decentralised AI for real-world health data
 - [CVDLINK](#) – A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions
 - [NextGen](#) – Next generation tools for Genome-centric Multimodal data integration in personalised cardiovascular medicine
- Projects funded under the same main programme: HORIZON.2.1.5 - Tools, Technologies and Digital Solutions for Health and Care, including personalised medicine
 - [COMFORTage](#) – Prediction, Monitoring and Personalized Recommendations for Prevention and Relief of Dementia and Frailty
 - [SPIDeRR](#) – Stratification of patients with musculoskeletal symptoms using advanced integrative data modelling
 - [CoMPaSS-NMD](#) – Computational Models for new Patients Stratification Strategies of Neuromuscular Disorders
 - [SQUEEZE](#) – Maximising Impact of Prescription Drugs in Rheumatoid Arthritis

- Other projects with a focus similar to HEREDITARY’s
 - IMI/IHI-funded:
 - [PROMINENT](#) – Precision medicine platform in neurodegenerative disease
 - [EHDEN](#) – European Health Data and Evidence Network
 - [IDERHA](#) – Integration of heterogeneous data and evidence towards regulatory and HTA acceptance
 - ECR-funded:
 - [MicrobiotaNeuroTalk](#) – Trafficking mechanisms and physiological factors mediating a direct gut microbiota-brain neuron interaction
 - [NeurO-GI](#) – In vivo gut-brain optogenetic endomicroscopy for digestive disorders management
 - [gutMAP](#) – Gut microbiome-mediated activities of psychotropic drugs
 - [MoodBugs](#) – How our gut microbes influence how we feel – bacterial metabolites and inflammation as mediators of human microbiota-affect relationships

2.2 Shortlist of projects and initiatives relevant to HEREDITARY scope

To identify, within the above list, the projects more in line with HEREDITARY strategic objectives, EBC conducted a consortium consultation. Through a survey, HEREDITARY partners were invited to indicate their areas of interest (Figure 2), liaison strategic goals (Figure 3) and the projects to liaise with (Figure 4).

Figure 2 Consortium consultation on HEREDITARY liaison objectives - responses to Question 1

As illustrated in Figure 2, multimodal health data integration (12 responses), gut-brain axis and federated networking infrastructure (10 responses each) and neurodegenerative disorders (8 responses) rank among the priority areas HEREDITARY liaison activities should address.

Figure 3 Consortium consultation on HEREDITARY liaison objectives - responses to Question 2

Figure 3 provides an overview of what, according to the HEREDITARY consortium, HEREDITARY liaison activities should primarily aim for, namely:

- Fostering data sharing and the exchange of information and knowledge between scientists (11 responses)
- Keeping the project aligned with projects and initiatives with similar or complementary objectives (9 responses)
- Increasing the visibility of HEREDITARY research field (7 responses)

The options “develop policy recommendations to advance research on HEREDITARY core topics” and “increase the engagement in research of people with neurodegenerative disorders” rank low (4 and 3 responses, respectively).

Top priorities of the Horizon Europe - Health programme include Destination 5: Unlocking the full potential of new tools, technologies and digital solutions for a healthy society. In this regard, HEREDITARY and its sister projects contribute, through their innovative research, to the achievement of EU strategic objectives. On a similar note, the projects provide, altogether, high-quality, relevant and scientifically robust evidence holding the transformative potential to enhance healthcare outcomes and operational efficiency, unlock new pathways for research and innovation and guide public health policy development across Europe. Similarly, patient engagement proves essential to ensure user-friendly research and its translation into innovation and healthcare interventions in real-world settings.

For the above reasons, HEREDITARY research should be lived experience-informed and translated into policy recommendations advancing this research field and healthcare.

Figure 4 Consortium consultation on HEREDITARY liaison objectives - responses to Question 3

Figure 4 offers a glimpse into a variety of projects, namely:

- Project funded under the same topic and same main programme as HEREDITARY (in blue and light blue, respectively)
- The IHI and ECR-funded projects (in green and yellow, respectively) in line with HEREDITARY strategic objectives

The list grows longer as new contacts are made, and new projects are launched.

2.3 Identification of common interest points and potential areas of collaboration

Figure 4 top ranked projects cover different funding programmes, and all the priority areas identified in Figure 2. For this reason, representatives from the full list of projects were approached for a bilateral meeting aiming at discussing potential synergies and opportunities for cooperation. In this regard, Table 1 represents the meeting calendar.

Table 1 Bilateral meetings with HEREDITARY-related projects - calendar

MEETING DATE	PROJECT
21 May 2024	CoMPaSS-NMD – Computational Models for new Patients Stratification Strategies of Neuromuscular Disorders
4 June 2024	MoodBugs – How our gut microbes influence how we feel – bacterial metabolites and inflammation as mediators of human microbiota-affect relationships

MEETING DATE	PROJECT
11 June 2024	STRATUM – 3D Decision Support Tool for Brain Tumor Surgery
21 June 2024	gutMAP – Gut microbiome-mediated activities of psychotropic drugs
27 June 2024	MicrobiotaNeuroTalk – Trafficking mechanisms and physiological factors mediating a direct gut microbiota-brain neuron interaction
3 July 2024	CVDLINK – A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions
9 July 2024	WISDOM – Well-being improvement through the Integration of healthcare and reSearch Data and models with Out border for chronic iMmune-mediated diseases

In summer 2024, the outreach to the COMFORTage and Next-Gen projects showed a duplication of efforts: representatives from both projects were also meeting peers from initiatives similar to HEREDITARY to design and deploy a liaison plan based on collective needs. After a first meeting, EBC decided to unite forces with EHTEL and DataPower Consulting (representing COMFORTage and Next-Gen, respectively) to streamline the workflow and maximise the impact of HEREDITARY research field. When the respective project lists were merged, multimodal health data integration appeared as a red thread across most of the projects, which inspired the topic of the first meeting: challenges in multimodal health data integration.

2.4 Design and implementation of a liaison plan

Based on bilateral meetings' outcomes, EBC designed a programme consisting of a set of joint activities addressing the overlapping needs of relevant projects and initiatives and being regularly updated based on new connections and priorities' reassessment.

2.4.1 September 2024: Strategic Meeting on Challenges in Multimodal Health Data Integration (virtual)

On 24 September 2024, HEREDITARY, [NextGen](#) and [COMFORTage](#) jointly conveyed a Strategic Workshop on Challenges in Multimodal Health Data Integration, which brought together a diverse range of EU-funded research projects with similar or complementary objectives to encourage the exchange of knowledge and enhance synergies with regards to multimodal health data integration.

The meeting was attended by 49 representatives from the 17 projects featured in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Overview of the projects represented in the HEREDITARY co-led Strategic Meeting

Participants benefited from the experience of two H2020- and a HE-funded research projects – namely [AI-Mind](#), [BRAINTEASER](#) and NextGen – whose representatives gave a presentation. Their achievements in the context of multimodal health data integration, the challenges faced, and the solutions envisioned were notably addressed.

Organisers then opened the floor to participants to explore approaches, mutual interests and potential areas for collaboration. In particular, attendees highlighted shared challenges such as semantic data management, anonymisation, and data integration from various sources e.g., hospital databases, wearables, sensors.

Various projects are also working on enhancing semantic interoperability, for systems to understand shared data the same way.

The following collaboration opportunities were identified:

- Sharing expertise on data storage, summarisation, and visualisation, especially regarding wearable data
- Cross-linking project websites for broader visibility
- Learning from experienced projects to improve Artificial Intelligence (AI) models and methodologies
- Joint development of publications and technical reports to disseminate findings and compare project architectures

- Organising joint workshops, events, and standardisation efforts

2.4.2 October 2024: Consensus Meeting on Priority Areas and Joint Activities (virtual)

On 24 October 2024, 26 projects representatives reconvened in a Consensus Meeting aiming to build consensus on priorities areas to focus on in the following months in a collaborative and synergic approach.

On that occasion, participants went through the answers to a questionnaire designed by EHTEL to get a glimpse of the topics to be prioritised at an early stage. It resulted in the establishment of the “Harnessing Health Data” Cluster and the agreement on a set of working groups based on priority setting and led by one or more projects’ representatives each. Table 2 provides an overview of the identified groups and group leaders (in bold), and members.

Table 2 Repartition of the HEREDITARY-related projects representatives in the “Harnessing Health Data” Cluster’s Task Forces

TASK FORCE	LEADERS AND MEMBERS
1. Integration of multimodal data, including genomics	HEREDITARY WISDOM ThrombUS+ Protect-Child COMFORTage
2. Federated (versus centralized) learning	CVDLINK and Protect-Child HEREDITARY WISDOM COMFORTage
3. Data requirements, data collection and bias management	BETTER and WISDOM HEREDITARY ThrombUS+ SYNTHIA NextGen COMFORTage iHELP WISDOM CVDLINK STAGE
4. Personalised medicine and predictive models	COMFORTage and ThrombUS+ WISDOM CVDLINK BETTER WISDOM ThrombUS+ CVDLINK STAGE iHELP

As outcomes of the collaborations listed above, joint communications including stakeholder engagement activities and scientific publications will be designed at a later stage.

2.4.3 November 2024: BRAINTEASER Impact & Exploitation Workshop “Harnessing AI for Brain Health: Lab to Market to Society” (Brain Innovation Days, Brussels)

In November 2024, HEREDITARY, BRAINTEASER and AI-Mind reconvened at Brain Innovation Days – an EBC-led two-day event designed to inspire collaboration and accelerate innovation across the brain ecosystem. In the context of [BRAINTEASER Impact & Exploitation Workshop “Harnessing AI for Brain Health: Lab to Market to Society”](#) on 13 November 2024, HEREDITARY Coordinator was invited to intervene, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Harnessing AI for Brain Health: Lab to Market to Society

Bringing Artificial Intelligence Home for a Better Care of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis and Multiple Sclerosis

13 November 2024, 16:05-17:50

The BRAINTEASER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No GA101017598.

Figure 6 Speaker lineup of the BRAINTEASER Impact & Exploitation Workshop - including HEREDITARY Project Officer at HaDEA and HEREDITARY Coordinator

Table 3 shows the agenda of the event, which notably featured a keynote from Claudia Prettnner, Project Advisor, BRAINTEASER and HEREDITARY Project Officer at the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), who introduced the audience to HaDEA and its portfolio of health research projects – with a focus on current and future brain health research. Her presentation also stressed the role of EU Research & Innovation in contributing to effective prevention strategies and better care of brain disorders, as well as the role of the EU brain community in enabling evidence-based policymaking to counter today’s brain health challenges.

Table 3 Agenda of the BRAINTEASER Impact & Exploitation Workshop – including the intervention of HEREDITARY Coordinator in Session 1

BRAINTEASER Impact & Exploitation Workshop - Agenda	
16:05 CET	Keynote <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Claudia Prettner, Project Adviser, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)
16:15 CET	BRAINTEASER Results and Exploitation Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barbara Di Camillo, University of Padova, Information Engineering Department; BRAINTEASER Scientific Coordinator
16:25 CET	Session 1: From lab to market - Unlocking the translation of research into brain innovation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gianmaria Silvello, Professor, University of Padua; HEREDITARY Coordinator • Liesbet Geris, Professor, University of Liège, KU Leuven, VPHi; Research & Technology Working Group Leader, Avicenna Alliance • Elisabetta Vaudano, Principal Scientific Manager, Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) • Mats Sundgren, Senior Industry Scientific Director, European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD)
16:50 CET	Session 2: From market to society - Enabling remote, value-based and patient-centred care <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natalia Allegretti, Senior Innovation Project Manager, ECHAlliance • Elisabeth Kasilingam, CEO, European Multiple Sclerosis Platform (EMSP) • Leon Brudy, Business Development Manager EMEA, Garmin Health • Umberto Manera, Assistant Professor, Department of Neuroscience - University of Turin
17:15 CET	Session 3: BRAINTEASER innovation showcase: the clinical app <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vincenzo Carbone, Sr. Product Manager MedTech, InSilicoTrials • Carlos de Miguel Sánchez, Neurologist, General University Hospital Gregorio Marañón • Umberto Manera, Assistant Professor, Department of Neuroscience - University of Turin • Vebjørn Andersson, Research Coordinator, Oslo University Hospital; AI-Mind Project Coordinator
17:40 CET	Session 4: BRAINTEASER exploitation roadmap - Key takeaways <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vincenzo Carbone, Senior R&I Project Manager, InSilicoTrials Technologies

Gianmaria Silvello, HEREDITARY Coordinator, was invited to take part in Session 1 “From lab to market - Unlocking the translation of research into brain innovation”, bringing together key actors on the way from lab to the market to stress the power of collaboration to accelerate the translation of research into innovation. Public-private partnerships, which bring academia, industry, end-users as well as regulatory bodies together, were highlighted as key enablers. On that occasion, panellists also addressed main challenges to overcome to ultimately harness unstructured data in a meaningful way: insufficient funding, bureaucracy and healthcare unreadiness.

[BRAINTEASER](#) (Bringing Artificial Intelligence home for a better care of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and multiple sclerosis) is an EU-funded project seeking to exploit the value of big data (large clinical datasets, patient-generated data from wearables and air pollution data from sensors) to advance remote monitoring and clinical decision making in MS and ALS through an AI-based model. As the project was coming to an end, the democratisation of BRAINTEASER solutions and the exploitation of the project results represented a pressing issue, addressed from a patient, clinician and industry perspective. Throughout the duration of the event, speakers highlighted the codesign with patients as an opportunity of mutual learning resulting in more user-friendly solutions. The panel also addressed resource allocation, the hardship of making successful research marketable, the highly fragmented market and healthcare systems across the EU as major obstacles to the translation of research into practice.

Brain Innovation Days proved an important learning and networking opportunity: HEREDITARY Coordinator notably had a chance to exchange with HaDEA representatives on the importance of liaison activities and clustering for a greater impact.

2.4.4 May 2025: Task Force 1.1 Alignment Meeting (virtual)

On 15 May 2025, the Task Force 1 "Integration of Multimodal Data, including Genomics", led by the HEREDITARY project, held its first meeting. Seven project representatives from the HEREDITARY, [COMFORTage](#), [WISDOM](#), and [ThrombUS+](#) projects attended. The meeting's objective was to discuss how each project is proceeding, highlighting the challenges encountered by each so far, to review the draft liaison plan, and to establish next steps.

Discussions on the integration of multimodal health data confirmed that the projects within the task force are encountering similar hurdles – namely, establishing who can access the data, translating patient data into simplified resources, and harmonising heterogenous data from different sources and types. The group also raised the challenge of justifying the use of AI and navigating the ethical and legal regulations surrounding it.

As a result of the discussions, the following collaboration opportunities were identified:

- An online repository of deliverables on the HEREDITARY project website
- A joint white paper describing the challenges and gaps in the field, and the solutions found by each project to overcome barriers

To formally record these, EBC and HEREDITARY Coordinator agreed to extend a previous collaboration agreement to each member of the Task Force, detailing discussed collaboration opportunities.

Ahead of the next meeting (set to take place in October 2025), it was agreed that projects will formalise the collaboration and start brainstorming on the content of the joint white paper.

2.4.5 May 2025: HEREDITARY, LETHE and BRAINTEASER Webinar “Federated Learning for Neurodegenerative Disease Research: A New Path to Risk Reduction and Better Care”

As HEREDITARY and BRAINTEASER, LETHE also leverages multimodal health data integration in brain health (with a focus on preventing dementia in the early stages of development). HEREDITARY, [LETHE](#) and [BRAINTEASER](#) jointly organised, on 16 May 2025, the [webinar](#) “Federated Learning for Neurodegenerative Disease Research: A New Path to Risk Reduction and Better Care”. The webinar’s aims were twofold: firstly, to educate the audience on federated learning, including its different types, and their benefits and challenges. Secondly, to showcase how HEREDITARY, LETHE and BRAINTEASER each use cutting-edge machine learning techniques to improve risk prediction, diagnosis, and patient care in neurodegenerative diseases.

Running from 10:30 to 11:30 CET, the webinar was structured according to Table 4.

Table 4 Agenda of the HEREDITARY, LETHE and BRAINTEASER Webinar “Federated Learning for Neurodegenerative Disease Research: A New Path to Risk Reduction and Better Care” – featuring Umberto Manera, HEREDITARY & BRAINTEASER Clinical Partner

Federated Learning for Neurodegenerative Disease Research: A New Path to Risk Reduction and Better Care - Agenda	
10:30-10:35 CET	Welcome and Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natalia Allegretti, Senior Innovation Projects Manager, ECHAlliance
10:35-10:50 CET	Introduction to Federated Learning and the Lethe Example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hannes Hilberger, Researcher, FH JOANNEUM
10:50-11:05 CET	Bridging Projects: How Federated Learning in HEREDITARY project can advance Brainteaser AI models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Umberto Manera, Assistant Professor, University of Turin
11:05-11:30 CET	Questions from the audience

On that occasion, Umberto Manera represented both HEREDITARY and BRAINTEASER as Clinical Partner. After providing a detailed explanation of HEREDITARY’s aims, focus areas (multimodality, data integration, multilingualism, privacy and security) and methods, with a focus on the project’s five interconnected layers and five use cases, Umberto Manera highlighted the potential benefits of HEREDITARY-BRAINTEASER cooperation. More specifically, Umberto Manera stressed how HEREDITARY’s federated learning techniques could advance BRAINTEASER’s artificial intelligence models and how such a collaboration could help building sustainable frameworks for data governance and improving international positioning.

2.4.6 June 2025: Brain Talks Podcast “HEREDITARY project: trustworthy AI in advancing brain research”

The BIDays-produced [Brain Talks](#) is a podcast series featuring key opinion leaders and stakeholders from the ever-growing brain ecosystem, discussing the latest breakthroughs, ongoing research and other exciting topics related to brain innovation.

In this context, a [HEREDITARY podcast episode](#) was released on 27 June 2025. The episode is titled "HEREDITARY Project: Trustworthy AI in Advancing Brain Research" and introduces listeners to the HEREDITARY project while offering new insights into the project addresses topics including artificial intelligence (AI) and advanced analytics, multimodal health data, and data privacy and security.

The 20-minute episode was professionally moderated by Sam Pauly and featured two guests: Elisabetta Biasin, Researcher at the KU Leuven Centre for IT & Law and a HEREDITARY Partner, and Helena Ledmyr, Director of Development and Communications at the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility.

Starting with an introduction to the project, the discussion later blended the project's methods and commitment to ensuring public trust and data privacy with an overall discussion on how to use AI and big data in a conscious, transparent, and safe way to advance health-driven research and innovation in Europe. Throughout the episode, HEREDITARY and its methods were therefore expanded to address AI-driven questions on a broader scale.

3 Conclusion

Since the beginning of the project, EBC has liaised with projects like HEREDITARY in nature and objectives with the aim to identify opportunities for cooperation, streamline efforts and overcome, in a collaborative approach, barriers to the implementation of research findings in real-world settings. The activities designed so far meet the needs identified by the cluster and are regularly reviewed to maximise their impact.

To increase the visibility of this research field and the activities undertaken with related projects, HEREDITARY and the growing number of signatories of its collaboration agreement have committed to cross-link project websites. In this regard, a HEREDITARY website section dedicated to cluster members and activities is in the pipeline.

HEREDITARY podcast episode represents a first attempt to establish, in the framework of liaison activities, links with relevant policy files – namely, the General Data Protection Regulation, the European Health Data Space and the EU Artificial Intelligence Act. Although many of the cluster projects are in their infancy, there is consensus on the need to bridge science and policy since early days: to initiate a dialogue with relevant policymakers on challenges and opportunities in the field, the cluster agreed on developing, in the next few months, a joint policy paper.

To facilitate the exchange of ideas and experience, an in-person networking meeting bringing together representatives from both recent and experienced projects in the field is set to take place in October 2025.